

FACTORS AFFECTING THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOLERANCE IN STUDENTS THROUGH MUSIC TOURISM.

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Abstract: The incomparable role of music in the spiritual development of a person has been recognized by scientists and experts. Music sounds express the most delicate feelings and experiences, regardless of the representative of any people or nation. Love for music, singing, art is formed in the family since childhood.

Key words: spiritual maturity, musical sounds, the most delicate feelings and experiences, love for music and art.

Large-scale reforms implemented in all areas in our country are laying the foundation for a new renaissance in the new Uzbekistan. As the head of state stated in his Address to the Oliy Majlis on December 29, 2020: "We have set ourselves the great goal of establishing the foundation of the Third Renaissance in our country, for this the new Khorezmids, Timurids, Ibn Sinas, Ulugbeks, Navoi and we need to create the environment and conditions that will nurture Baburs. In this, first of all, development of education, establishment of a healthy lifestyle, promotion of science and innovation should serve as the main pillars of our national idea. [1]

"It is not an exaggeration to say that it is difficult to find a person in our country who does not have a drum, circle or other musical instrument at home, and who lives without feeling the life-giving effect of music in his life," said Uzbekistan. The first President of the Republic I.A. Karimov.[2]

In fact, the art of music has a greater and stronger influence than other types of art in educating the next generation in the spirit of high spirituality.

The effects of the tunes played by different musical instruments on the human body are wide and varied. Music, through its rhythm, tone and melody, can affect a person's mental state, physical well-being and even brain function. We consider the following effects:

Effect on mental state:

- Reduce stress: Research shows that listening to slow, relaxing music in particular can help reduce stress and overcome feelings of depression. For example, classical music, jazz or meditative music is effective in this regard.

- Improves mood: Upbeat music, such as pop, rock or country music, can improve people's mood and give them energy.

- Calm and Calm: Slow tones, such as meditative music or music mixed with nature sounds, can promote feelings of calmness and improve sleep quality.

Effects on physical well-being:

- Control heart rate and blood pressure: Slow and soothing music can lower heart rate and blood pressure, which can help improve overall health.

- Pain Relief: Music is used as an aid in pain relief, especially during the healing period after physically painful procedures such as surgery.

- Improve physical activity: Rhythmic and fast music can motivate and encourage you to move more during sports or exercise.

Effects on brain activity:

- Memory and learning: Music, especially learning new musical instruments or practicing music, can improve memory, attention and other cognitive functions.

- Stimulate creativity: Listening to music, especially using different genres and tones, stimulates the brain to work creatively.

- Therapeutic tool: Music therapy is used to treat various psychological problems, including stress and depression. This suggests that music has a positive effect on brain chemicals.

These volitional pictorial possibilities of music are recognized by Greek scientists - Pythagoras, Plato, Aristotle and Eastern thinkers - Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abdurrahman Jami, Alisher Navai, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Kaikovus, figures of Sufism - Imam Ghazali, Kalabadi Bukhari and others.

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Philosopher and scientist - Aristotle "Music is an important tool to achieve this goal. Music affects not only conscious entertainment, but also the moral quality of a person. Because in music there are human behavior, dreams and hopes" - he said. [3]

Music has served to strengthen friendship, fraternity among peoples, nations, and states since time immemorial. It also serves to strengthen intercultural understanding and communication skills among students.

As soon as a person comes into the world and realizes himself, he is eager to travel. As the researchers K. Gadoyev and S. Berdiyeva noted: "If we look at a baby who has just started walking, he always wants to go out of the house. Because, in the eyes of a child, leaving the house before the world view is formed is a journey. As a person matures, his desire to travel increases. He shares the

impressions he got during his travels with his relatives, and some of them write down what they have seen and experienced and share it with the general public. And the impressions received during the trip will undoubtedly be imprinted in a person's memory for a lifetime" [4].

Rich materials about tourism and music tourism are reflected in historical, literary, religious and scientific sources. In particular, according to historical sources, it became known that music tourism dates back to many years.

In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, "Safar 1 (Arabic - travel, walk, go somewhere; marta, Gal. 1. To go somewhere on the way of service or to travel, to meet; road. long journey, a month's journey, to go on a journey, to return from a journey. Sheikh Muhammad Sadiq Muhammad Yusuf paid special attention to "Travel etiquette" in his book "Social Etiquette". For example, "Journey is to leave one's homeland or place of residence and travel a long distance. In fact, this is a good deed, but it can be elevated to the level of worship with intention. The success of the trip depends on the intention. For example, a person went on a trip. His intention is to refrain from begging, to be kind to his family, and to give alms in excess of his needs. Such a trip will become the work of the hereafter with this intention. A man also went on a journey. The intention is to perform Hajj hypocritically and to the farmer. There is no intention that such a trip is for the hereafter. Rasulullah alayhi wa sallam said, "Surely, actions depend on intentions." [6] As we mentioned above, our ancestors traveled and were encouraged to travel. The reason is that the trip is beneficial for health and removing the dust from the heart. The messages say: "Travel, you will be healthy." The trip was made mainly for Hajj - Umrah, learning, business, self-reflection, writing, sightseeing, visiting teachers and great people, and other purposes.

Husayn Voiz Koshifi expressed the eleven beneficial aspects of the trip as follows.

- "First of all, it is beneficial for the health of the body, because during the trip, the air changes and the organs are trained, because the movement removes moisture from the body, improves blood circulation;

- Secondly, there is a reason to visit the graves of great people, famous scientists, dear saints;

- Thirdly, travel removes laziness, laziness, because if a person lives in one place, laziness and illness increase, the nutrients (metabolism) and water of the body stop moving;

- Fourthly, it removes sadness and sadness, because no matter how sad a person is, if he goes on a trip, he will be happy and forget his worries;
- Fifthly, the soul is trained on the journey, difficulties and hardships teach a person to be patient, resilient, broad-minded;
- Sixth, life will pass peacefully on the trip, thoughts about life and death will be clarified;
- Seventhly, opportunities for studying science expand during the trip, you can learn a lot from teachers in other countries;
- Eighth, the ways of learning different professions and manners from different categories of people will be opened;
- From the ninth, the conversation of the great and the wise is reached;
- Tenth, separation from parents, relatives and friends, a feeling of longing for them is born, the value of people, the value of the country increases;
- From the eleventh, the value of strangers will be appreciated, compassion will increase in the heart"

Scholars have paid great attention to travel etiquette since ancient times. First of all, they emphasized that the trip should not be wasted, but should be with a specific goal in mind. It is better than a trip that has no destination and wastes time, money and energy. After the purpose of the trip is clear, preparation for the trip begins.

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